

Critical thinking about health and treatments among Norwegian youth: a cross-sectional assessment (Protocol)

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Introduction

Young people are increasingly exposed to mis- and disinformation online and in social media. Some of the information they passively consume is related to health advice, or claims about the effects of health information.

The Informed Health Choices project, started in 2012, has developed 49 key concepts that are considered by researchers and other stakeholders to be important to understand and apply in order to make informed decisions about one's health.(OXman) These concepts are broadly categorized as concepts related to (a) recognizing unreliable claims, (b) recognizing reliable evidence, and (c) making well-informed choices.(Oxman)

In 2017, Dahlgren and colleagues conducted a survey of Norwegian adults to explore their understanding of a selection of key concepts.(Dahlgren) The results indicate that more than half of the adult population at the time struggled to understand approximately half of the 24 concepts they were asked about. (Dahlgren 2018) It is unclear how well Norwegian youth 16-20 understand and can apply relevant IHC key concepts.

Objectives

The objective of this study is to measure the ability of Norwegian youth to assess health and treatment claims and make informed choices.

Methods

Study design

This is a web-based cross-sectional survey using FHI-panelet and *Nettskjema* survey software to collect responses. FHI-panelet is a population panel established in 2024, by the Centre for epidemic interventions research at the NIPH. The panel consists of about 22.000 people living in Norway. All panel members have consented to receive invitations to participate in CEIR-studies. The youngest participants are born in May, 2008.

The CLAIM database includes a large number of Key concepts and corresponding MCQs. Longer questionnaires have lower response rates (27). Therefore, for this study, we will develop two complementary questionnaires to be administered as part of a cross-sectional survey of young people. Both questionnaires will include a common set of seven items designed to assess participants' self efficacy and intended behaviours (see Box 1). In addition, each questionnaire will include 14 MCQs (two MCQs with four options for each key concept, seven concepts) to assess understanding and application of seven key concepts, selected from a pool of fourteen key concepts.

In order to prioritize which 14 concepts to include in the surveys, we will invite researchers specializing in working with critical thinking and youth to participate in an advisory panel to inform this process. Our starting point will be the 24 key concepts that were prioritized and included in a 2018 survey of Norwegian adults (a total of 49 key concepts are included from the IHC project) (REF). The research team will first determine if there are any of the 24 concepts that are clearly not relevant for Norwegian youth and advisory panel members will be asked to rate the relevance (likert scale 1-7) of the remaining 24 key concepts for Norwegian youth using an anonymous online Google form. We will promote all concepts that are rated as 6 or 7 (Relevant or very relevant) by at least one advisory panel member to an online group discussion where we will attempt to achieve consensus on the 14 most relevant IHC concepts to include in the surveys.

Survey

Each survey will include 21 questions divided into two sections: self-efficacy and intended behaviour, and questions designed to assess understanding and application of seven (14 total, equally divided into two studies) IHC Key concepts. See Box 1 for an example of a question (questions in the survey will be presented in Norwegian).

The IHC Key Concepts will be divided equally across the two questionnaires to ensure coverage of the full set while minimizing participant burden. This design allows for consistency in the measurement of core outcomes while also enabling exploration of a broader range of principles across the study population.

Box 1. Example of a multiple choice question

Imagine you hear about a drink made from beetroot on the radio. The makers of the drink say that if you have some of it every day, you will live a long life.

Question: Based on this, how sure can you be that beetroot will give you a long life?

Options:

- A) Very sure, but the drink may also frighten you by making your pee (urine) red
- B) Not very sure. Very few treatments help everyone who takes them
- C) Very sure. If it was not true, the makers of the drink would not have said this

Svar:

All MCQs in the Claim evaluation database have been validated and translated to Norwegian. In addition to the MCQs we will collect the following information for all participants: age, gender, and level of education.

Box 2. Overview of included Key Concepts and MCQs in each questionnaire

Key concepts / Question regarding self-efficacy and intended behaviour	Questionnaire 1 (Number of MCQs)	Questionnaire 2 (Number of MCQs)
Key concept 1.1b Do not assume that treatments have large, dramatic effects	2	0
Key Concept 1.2b Do not assume that association is the same as causation (PDF)	0	2
Key Concept 1.2a. Do not assume that a plausible explanation is sufficient	2	0
Key Concept 1.1e) Do not assume that comparisons are not needed	0	2
Key Concept 1.2d) Do not assume that single study is sufficient	2	0
Key Concept 1.3c) Do not assume that a treatment is helpful or safe based on how widely used it is or has been.	0	2
Key Concept 1.3d) Do not assume a treatment is better based on how new or technologically impressive it is	2	0
Key Concept 1.3b) Do not assume that more treatment is better.	0	2
Key Concept 1.4e) Do not assume that there are no competing interests	2	0
Key Concept 1.4a) Do not assume that personal experiences alone are sufficient	0	2
Key Concept 1.4c) Do not assume that opinions alone are sufficient	2	0
Key Concept 2.1a) Consider whether the people being compared were similar	0	2
Key Concept 2.4a) Be cautious of small studies	2	0
Key Concept 3.1c) Consider the relevance of fair comparisons in laboratories, animals, or highly selected people	0	2
Below are some actions. Please read each one carefully and give the answer that comes closest to how difficult or easy you find each of the actions to be. There are not right or wrong answers to these questions.		
Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing if a claim about a treatment is based on a research study comparing treatments?	1	1
Question: How difficult or easy do you think it is to find information about treatments that is based on research studies comparing treatments?	1	1
Question: How difficult or easy do you find judging the trustworthiness of the results of a research study comparing treatments?	1	1
Question: How difficult or easy do you find knowing if the results of a research study comparing treatments are relevant to you?	1	1
Think about a sickness that you might get. Imagine someone claiming (saying) that a treatment might help you get better.		
Question: How likely are you to find out what the claim was based on (for example by asking the person making the claim)?	1	1
Question: How likely are you to find out if the claim was based on a research study comparing the treatment to no treatment?	1	1
3 Question: How likely are you to say "yes" if you are asked to participate in a research study comparing two treatments for your sickness?	1	1

Participant Recruitment, Selection, Consent, and Compensation

We will invite approximately 600 panel members born between 2005 and 2008 (between 17 and 20 at the time of the study) to participate in the study via email. We will inform participants about the goal of the study, the estimated time needed to complete the survey, and their rights as participants (data storage, deletion of data, etc.). The participants must explicitly indicate informed consent by ticking off a box in the Nettskjema form before proceeding to the survey.

All panel members born between 2005 and 2008 will be eligible for participation.

Panel members will be invited upon completion of the survey to click on a link to a second Nettskjema where they can submit their email address in order to be eligible to win one of three available gift cards worth approximately 2000 nok. Three email addresses will be randomly selected at the end of the survey period and winning participants will be notified via email.

Sample size calculation

No sample size calculation was conducted since we are not testing a specific hypothesis in this study.

Analysis plan

For each survey we will present a table of participant characteristics. We will score responses to each MCQ as correct or incorrect, and missing responses will be scored as incorrect.

For MCQs about Key concepts, a participant will be considered to have demonstrated understanding of a concept if they correctly answer both MCQs for that concept. We will estimate the percentage of Norwegian youth that understands each concept.

For questions about self-efficacy and intended behaviour, we will dichotomize the responses (very unlikely or unlikely vs likely or very likely) and report the number and percentage for each of the response options.

Effect modifiers

We have no hypotheses regarding effect modifiers and participants number of correct responses to the MCQs about key concepts or self-efficacy and intended behaviour. We will, however, explore associations between age, gender and level of education and participants' scores.

Dissemination Plan

We plan to present our findings at conferences in Norway and internationally, and other relevant forums. We also intend to publish the results of this study in a peer-reviewed journal.

Method Selection, Risks, and Risk Management

Web-based online surveys are increasingly common, however, there are inherent risks of bias due to convenience sampling, including self-selection bias, exclusion bias based on internet access, and professionalization of survey-respondents. Although the last risk is minor given that this is only the third survey being conducted with this panel. However, we will attempt to mitigate some of this risk by inviting all panel members, and also conducting the survey with a group of eligible participants recruited from a Norwegian school in order to explore possible difference between panelists and the general public.

Ethics

The study does not fall under the Health Research Act, but we will still request that the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics evaluate the project and provide confirmation that it is not subject to submission requirements. We will assess the implications of handling personal data internally at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health. All participants will receive information about the project. School nurses, teachers, and the reference group providing input will give their signed consent before we begin data collection. Students at the lower secondary schools may participate in group interviews (after the lessons) if their parents have given prior written consent. We have chosen not to use audio recordings in group discussions with the youths.

Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion

We aim to facilitate collaboration and data collection with considerations for equity, diversity, and inclusion. This means that we will use universal design principles to inform the format of the survey, invitation, consent form, and other study materials. We will also user test all study materials with diverse interest holders to ensure that the text and content is easily understood and accessible.

Reflexivity

The researchers in this project have worked with the theme of critical health literacy in several projects. We have developed resources previously and maintain a positive perspective on the resources and their perceived usefulness and importance, which may influence how we interpret findings. However, the researchers have diverse professional backgrounds, including education, public health, global health, and design.

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